

financing. Meanwhile, total asset turnover is an activity ratio that measures the effectiveness of total assets in generating revenue (Sujarweni, 2017). Several previous studies have shown mixed results. Esthirahayu et al.'s (2014) study found that liquidity, leverage, and activity ratios significantly impact financial performance. However, other research indicates that not all ratios significantly impact financial performance (Agustina, 2021). These differing research findings indicate a research gap that requires further investigation, particularly in the regional hospital sector. Cut Meutia General Hospital, North Aceh Regency, as a government-owned hospital, has implemented the BLUD system since 2016. During the 2016–2023 period, the hospital's financial ratios fluctuated, both in terms of liquidity, solvency, and activity. Therefore, a more in-depth analysis is needed to determine whether the Current Ratio, Debt to Asset Ratio, and Total Asset Turnover affect financial performance, which is proxied by Return on Assets (ROA). Based on the description, this study aims to analyze the influence of Current Ratio, Debt to Asset Ratio, and Total Asset Turnover on financial performance at Cut Meutia General Hospital, North Aceh Regency for the period 2016–2023. This study is expected to provide theoretical contributions in the development of public sector accounting science and become a practical consideration in making hospital financial management policies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial performance

Financial performance reflects an organization's financial condition over a specific period, reflecting the success of its resource management (Fahmi, 2017). According to Raymond Budiman (2021), financial reports are documents that describe a company's financial position and performance over a specific period. According to Werner R. Murhadi (2019), financial reports are a form of business language. Financial reports provide users with processed data about a company's financial position. Financial performance can be used as a basis for managerial decision-making and to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of financial management. In the public sector, financial performance demonstrates an organization's ability to provide optimal services to the public (Mahsun, 2016). One indicator used to measure financial performance is Return on Assets (ROA), a ratio that measures a company's ability to generate profits from its total assets (Kasmir, 2015).

Liquidity Ratio (Current Ratio)

Liquidity ratios are used to measure an organization's ability to meet its short-term obligations (Hery, 2015). The Current Ratio (CR) is the comparison between current assets and current liabilities (Kasmir, 2015). This ratio indicates the extent to which a company is able to pay short-term obligations using its available current assets. The higher the current ratio, the better the company's liquidity. However, a ratio that is too high can also indicate underutilization of current assets (Hanafi, 2017).

Solvency Ratio (Debt to Asset Ratio)

The solvency or leverage ratio is used to measure the extent to which a company's assets are financed by debt (Kasmir, 2015). The Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) is the comparison between total liabilities and total assets. This ratio indicates the proportion of a company's funding that comes from external parties. According to Wijayanti & Sriyanto (2015), the solvency ratio indicates a hospital's ability to meet long-term obligations. The higher the DAR, the greater the company's dependence on debt, potentially increasing financial risk (Sujarweni, 2017).

Activity Ratio (Total Asset Turnover)

Activity ratios are used to measure a company's effectiveness in utilizing its assets to generate revenue (Kasmir, 2015). Total Asset Turnover (TATO) is the ratio of total revenue to total assets. This ratio indicates how efficiently a company's assets support its operational activities (Sujarweni, 2017). The higher the TATO value, the more effectively the company utilizes its assets to generate revenue.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with an associative research type, namely to determine the effect of *Current Ratio* (CR), *Debt to Asset Ratio* (DAR), and *Total Asset Turnover* (TATO) on Financial Performance proxied by *Return on Assets* (ROA). The object of the study is Cut Meutia General Hospital, North Aceh Regency with an observation period of 2016–2023. The type of data used is quantitative data, while the data source is secondary data obtained from annual financial reports (Balance Sheet and Operational Report). The data collection

technique is carried out through the documentation method, namely collecting and processing financial report data to calculate research ratios.

The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis with the equation:

$$ROA = \alpha + \beta_1 CR + \beta_2 DAR + \beta_3 TATO + e$$

Before hypothesis testing, classical assumption tests were conducted, including tests for normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation. Hypothesis testing was performed using the t-test (partial), F-test (simultaneous), and coefficient of determination (R^2) to determine the extent of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis Methods

In this study, the analytical method used was the quantitative descriptive method, namely a method of analyzing data obtained in numerical form (Sugiyono, 2016). This study used SPSS 15 to process the data.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Return On Asset	-26,0950	43,22868	8
Current Ratio	128,3375	43,99038	8
Debt to Asset Ratio	25,0888	4,79996	8
Total Asset Turnover	74,6738	20,27932	8

Based on Table 1, the average *Return on Assets* (ROA) value of -26.0950 indicates that hospitals tended to experience negative financial performance during the study period. *The Current Ratio* averaged 128.3375 with a standard deviation of 43.99038, indicating a relatively good level of liquidity with data variation still within reasonable limits. *The Debt to Asset Ratio* has an average of 25.0888 and a standard deviation of 4.79996, indicating that the proportion of debt to assets is relatively stable and does not experience high fluctuations. Meanwhile, *Total Asset Turnover* has an average of 74.6738 with a standard deviation of 20.27932, indicating that the ability of asset turnover to generate income is quite varied, but still within a controlled deviation.

Classical Assumption Test

The classical assumption test in this study was used to assess the feasibility of the regression model and the suitability of the independent variables, with the aim of observing residual value patterns. Therefore, the classical assumption test needs to be conducted before the multiple linear regression test. The classical assumption test includes the following:

Normality Test

In this study, the data normality test used was the *Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test statistical test*

Table 2. Normality Test

		Current Ratio	Debt to Asset Ratio	Total Asset Turnover	Return On Asset
N		8	8	8	8
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	128,3375	25,0888	74,6738	-26,0950
	Std. Deviation	43,99038	4,79996	20,27932	43,22868
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,262	,175	,338	,226
	Positive	,262	,175	,338	,198
	Negative	-,181	-,127	-,169	-,226
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,742	,494	,956	,640
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,641	,968	,320	,807

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Based on Table 4.5, the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for *the Current Ratio* is 0.641, *the Debt to Asset Ratio* is 0.968, and *the Total Asset Turnover* is 0.320. All of these values are greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the residual data is normally distributed. Thus, the multiple linear regression model in this study has met the assumption of normality.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2018), the multicollinearity test aims to determine the correlation that occurs between independent variables.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

		Current Ratio	Debt to Asset Ratio	Total Asset Turnover	Return On Asset
N		8	8	8	8
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	128,3375	25,0888	74,6738	-26,0950
	Std. Deviation	43,99038	4,79996	20,27932	43,22868
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,262	,175	,338	,226
	Positive	,262	,175	,338	,198
	Negative	-,181	-,127	-,169	-,226
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,742	,494	,956	,640
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,641	,968	,320	,807

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Based on Table 4.6, the VIF value for *the Current Ratio* is 1.537, *the Debt to Asset Ratio* is 1.063, and *the Total Asset Turnover* is 1.481. All VIF values are <10 and the Tolerance value is >0.01, so it can be concluded that the regression model does not experience multicollinearity problems and is suitable for further analysis.

Heteroscedasticity Test

According to Ghozali (2018:137), the heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in a regression model there is inequality in the variance of the residuals from one observation to another.

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-32,572	10,427		-1,256	,074
Current Ratio	,457	,345	,628	,807	,745
Debt to Asset Ratio	-,264	,064	-,688	-,332	,647
Total Asset Turnover	,529	,234	,237	,446	,343

Based on the Glejser test, the significance value of *the Current Ratio* is 0.745, *the Debt to Asset Ratio* is 0.647, and *the Total Asset Turnover* is 0.343, all of which are greater than 0.05. This indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model, thus meeting the homoscedasticity assumption.

Autocorrelation Test

The autocorrelation test aims to test whether in the regression model there is a correlation between the nuisance error in period t and the nuisance error in period t-1 (previous) (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 5 Autocorrelation Test

Model	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	,938	20,310	3	4	,007	2,619

b. Dependent Variable: *Return On Asset*

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that the value of $Du < d < U = 2.2866 < 2.619 < 1.7132$, so from these results there is no autocorrelation in this study.

Regression Method

Multiple Linear Regression Test

According to Sugiyono (2018), multiple linear regression is used by researchers to predict the condition (rise and fall) of the dependent variable or multiple linear regression is carried out if the number of independent variables is at least two.

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-380,657	53,242		-7,150	,002
Current Ratio	,968	,151	,985	6,401	,003
Debt to Asset Ratio	-6,597	1,153	-,733	-5,924	,004
Total Asset Turnover	,869	,322	,407	1,698	,054

a. Dependent Variable: *Return On Asset*

Based on the results of calculations from multiple linear regression tests, the following is obtained:

$$ROA = -380,657 + 0.968 \cdot \text{Current Ratio} - 6,597 \cdot \text{Debt to Asset Ratio} + 0.869 \cdot \text{Total Asset Turnover} + e$$

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Based on the regression results, a constant of -380.657 is obtained, indicating that if the *Current Ratio*, *Debt to Asset Ratio*, and *Total Asset Turnover* are zero, then the ROA is projected at -380.657. The *Current Ratio coefficient* of 0.968 indicates that every 1 unit increase in CR will increase ROA by 0.968, thus having a positive effect on financial performance. *The Debt to Asset Ratio* has a coefficient of -6.597, meaning that every 1 unit increase in DAR will decrease ROA by 6.597, thus having a negative effect. Meanwhile, *Total Asset Turnover* has a coefficient of 0.869, indicating that a 1 unit increase in TATO will increase ROA by 0.869 assuming other variables are constant.

Hypothesis Testing
Partial t-test

According to Ghozali (2015), the t-statistic test basically shows how far the influence of one independent variable individually explains the dependent variable.

Table 7. T-test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-380,657	53,242		-7,150	,002
Current Ratio	,968	,151	,985	6,401	,003
Debt to Asset Ratio	-6,597	1,153	-,733	-5,924	,004
Total Asset Turnover	,869	,322	,407	1,698	,054

a. Dependent Variable: Return On Asset

Based on Table 4.9, *Current Ratio* (X1) has a significant positive effect on financial performance ($t = 6.401$; sig. $0.003 < 0.05$). *Debt to Asset Ratio* (X2) has a significant negative effect ($t = -5.924$; sig. $0.04 < 0.05$). Meanwhile, *Total Asset Turnover* (X3) does not have a significant effect ($t = 1.698$; sig. $0.054 > 0.05$).

F test

The F test is basically to test the significance of the influence of all independent variables having a simultaneous or joint influence on the independent variable.

Table 8. F Test

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22,168	3	4,723	15,310	,007 ^a
	Residual	18,864	4	,566		
	Total	21,032	7			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total Asset Turnover, Debt to Asset Ratio, Current Ratio

b. Dependent Variable: Return On Asset

Based on the table above, it explains that the calculated F test result is 15.310 with a significance value of $0.007 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variables *Current Ratio*, *Debt to Asset Ratio* and *Total Asset Turnover* have a simultaneous effect on financial performance.

Determinant Test (R²)

According to Ghozali (2015), the Determination Coefficient Test (R²) is used to describe the model's ability to explain variations that occur in the dependent variable.

Table 9. Determinant Test (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,569 ^a	,442	,492	,79388

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total Asset Turnover, Debt to Asset Ratio, Current Ratio

b. Dependent Variable: Return On Asset

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Based on the table above, the results of the Determination Coefficient Test obtained an R Square value of 0.442. This means that the variables of *Current Ratio*, *Debt to Asset Ratio* and *Total Asset Turnover* are 44.2%, while the rest is influenced by other variables not discussed in this study.

Discussion

The discussion of this study shows that liquidity and funding structure play a significant role in determining the financial performance of Cut Meutia General Hospital. A positive and significant *Current Ratio* indicates that the hospital's ability to meet its short-term obligations can improve operational stability and support profit generation. Conversely, a significant negative *Debt to Asset Ratio* indicates that greater reliance on debt increases the financial burden, thus depressing financial performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the Current Ratio (CR) has a positive and significant effect on financial performance (ROA), indicating that the hospital's ability to meet short-term obligations can improve financial performance. The Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) has a negative and significant effect on ROA, meaning that the higher the proportion of debt to assets, the lower the financial performance tends to be. Meanwhile, Total Asset Turnover (TATO) did not significantly impact ROA, indicating that asset utilization effectiveness has not directly driven profit growth. However, simultaneously, CR, DAR, and TATO significantly impacted the financial performance of Cut Meutia General Hospital, North Aceh Regency, for the 2016–2023 period.

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